

Montenegro's ERA Integration

Progress and recommendations

Progress

Structural reforms in the research sector

- Launch of the Programme for Innovation 2021–2024 of the Innovation Fund
- Application of international peer review mechanisms for proposals under the Programme for Innovation 2021–2024 of the Innovation Fund
- Successful implementation of the Smart Specialisation Strategy
- Effective promotion of Open Access as part of Open Science

Gender equality

- Launch of the national strategy for gender equality 2021–2025
- 54% female doctoral graduates (She Figures 2021)

Internationalisation activities

- Increased participation in European Framework Programmes since FP7
- Higher proposal success rate than average of EU Member States in Horizon Europe
- 73% of scientific papers with at least one international co-author
- Association of the Innovation Fund to the European Network of Innovation Agencies

Recommendations

Establish a comprehensive R&I approach

- Improve the effectiveness of the R&I system through focusing on monitoring and evaluation
- Enhance coordination of national policies and resources to establish a national innovation system
- Launch the Strategy for Scientific Research Activities (2022-2026)
- Create more political support for gender equality measures

Further improve internationalisation activities

- Publish job vacancies on the EURAXESS portal
- Increase attractiveness of positions for doctoral students from EU Member States
- Establish active participation in ERA meetings
- Engage in the new European Innovation Agenda

Foster cooperation between academia and industry

- Increase transfer of research results to the market
- Enhance collaboration between academia and industry within the R&I system to create new partnerships
- Support companies to increase innovation activities

